

Characterization of MLP-Based DGGs Encoders for Data Cubes through Mean Correct Resolution (MCR) Analysis

Israel N. Silva¹

ITA, São José dos Campos, SP

Gabriel Dietzsch², Tahisa N. Kuck³, Elcio H. Shiguemori⁴

IEAv, São José dos Campos, SP

A Discrete Global Grid System (DGGs) is a spatial reference framework which provides a discrete Earth representation on a grid of geometric cells [1]. This structure avoids the significant distortions of conventional projections, thereby rendering it suitable for Data Cubes. Nevertheless, the challenge persists in efficiently mapping coordinates from diverse Coordinate Reference Systems (CRS) to DGGs indices. This study examines Multilayer Perceptrons (MLPs) for this geocoding task. It includes a comparative analysis on H3, a hexagonal grid optimized for neighborhood analysis, and rHEALPix (rearranged Hierarchical Equal Area isoLatitude Pixelization), a quadrilateral grid that prioritizes equal-area cells [2]. As exact bit-for-bit index replication is an overly rigorous metric, we introduce the Mean Correct Resolution (MCR) to assess the models' practical accuracy.

Building on existing studies of MLPs for CRS-to-CRS transformations [3], MLPs were chosen as universal function approximators [4] capable of learning the complex, non-linear mapping from continuous CRS coordinates to discrete DGGs indices. A two-stage (exploratory and refined) hyperparameter search with Optuna was used to find an optimal network configuration, maximizing performance while preventing overfitting. A synthetic dataset of "image fragments" was generated to force the model to learn decision boundaries between cells. Input coordinates were pre-processed with Fourier Features, and the MLP used a multi-head architecture with a hierarchical loss weighting strategy. Performance was assessed using the MCR metric: $MCR = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n R_{\text{correct}}(i)$, where n is the number of samples and $R_{\text{correct}}(i)$ is the max correct resolution for sample i . Finally, a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) was used to control for variability from the Source CRS, allowing a more precise analysis of the Training Volume and Latitude Range factors.

As illustrated in Figure 1, the results demonstrate a significant disparity in performance, indicating the percentage of test samples with perfect predictions across various resolutions. For instance, at approximately 120 km cell length, the accuracy of H3 is only 8.7%, compared to 46.5% for rHEALPix, which is reasonable considering the topological complexity of H3, characterized by its 12 pentagonal singularities and increased cell distortion. The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) results (Table 1) statistically substantiate this difference. For both DGGs, the volume of training data had a highly significant effect on the MCR ($p < .001$), whereas the latitude range and its interaction were significant solely for rHEALPix, likely due to its polar cube projection convergence. The Source CRS block was not statistically significant. A Tukey's HSD (Honestly Significant Difference) post-hoc test for the latitude range in the rHEALPix model did not reveal significant differences between individual pairs, suggesting that the effect observed in the ANOVA is complex and related to the training volume effect. Furthermore, each tenfold increase in training data size resulted in an average improvement of approximately 1.0 in MCR for rHEALPix and 0.6 for H3.

¹israelnunes@ita.br

²dietzschgd@fab.mil.br

³tahisatnk@fab.mil.br

⁴elcioehs@fab.mil.br

Figure 1. Cumulative Hierarchical Accuracy by Model.

Table 1. ANOVA table for H3 and rHEALPix models, presented side-by-side.

Source	H3 Model				rHEALPix Model			
	Sum Sq	df	F-value	p-value	Sum Sq	df	F-value	p-value
Training Volume	4.76	2	2383.81	< .001	12.15	2	4209.56	< .001
Latitude Range	0.00087	2	0.44	0.662	0.31	2	106.54	< .001
Block (CRS)	0.00088	1	0.88	0.375	0.00073	1	0.51	0.496
Training Volume × Latitude Range	0.0130	4	3.25	0.073	0.0967	4	16.76	< .001
Residual	0.0080	8			0.0100	8		

Our study demonstrates that a monolithic MLP, while proficient at identifying the base DGGS cell, is inadequate for replicating the entire hierarchical structure. The MCR metric proved effective, revealing the superior "learnability" of the rHEALPix grid compared to H3. The principal contributions include: (1) the first systematic characterization of MLP performance for H3/rHEALPix geocoding; (2) the introduction and validation of the MCR metric; and (3) a formal quantification of the effects of training volume and latitude. Practically, these models can serve as an initial geocoder to identify coarse regions for refinement by traditional algorithms. Future research should explore Chained or Cascaded Models, wherein specialist networks sequentially predict each hierarchical level.

References

- [1] Kevin Sahr, Denis White, and A. Jon Kimerling. "Geodesic Discrete Global Grid Systems". In: **Cartography and Geographic Information Science** 30.2 (2003), pp. 121–134. DOI: [10.1559/152304003100011090](https://doi.org/10.1559/152304003100011090).
- [2] Robert Gibb. **OGC Abstract Specification Topic 21: Discrete Global Grid Systems Part 1: Core Reference System and Operations and Equal Area Earth Reference System**. 20-040r3. 2021. URL: <https://portal.ogc.org/doi/20-040r3>.
- [3] Alfonso Tierra and Ricardo Romero. "Planes coordinates transformation between PSAD56 to SIR-GAS using a Multilayer Artificial Neural Network". In: **GEODESY AND CARTOGRAPHY** 63 (Dec. 2014), pp. 199–209. DOI: [10.2478/geocart-2014-0014](https://doi.org/10.2478/geocart-2014-0014).
- [4] Simon S. Haykin. **Neural Networks and Learning Machines**. 3rd. Upper Saddle River, NJ, USA: Prentice Hall, 2009.